

FEATURES OF EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMS IN PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATIONS OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

The article provides a theoretical analysis of the approved educational programs in preschool organizations for the period 2021-2022, analyzes the advantages and disadvantages. At the same time, the scope of difficulties in the implementation of educational and educational programs is highlighted by identifying similarities and differences.

Keywords: program, model, activity, skill, competence, creative.

By the decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 137 on March 15, 2021, a model for the development of preschool education and training was adopted.

The model is a normative document defining priority areas for the development and improvement of education and upbringing in preschool organizations. On the basis of the model, changes were made to regulatory documents. In addition to the order of the Minister of Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated October 14, 2022 No. 422, a standard curriculum for preschool education and training was approved. Before we dwell on the specifics of the program, let's analyze the programs approved for preschool organizations in the period from 2010 to 2022.

Before independence, Kazakhstan was the best pre-school education system in Central Asia and covered about 70% of children under 7 years of age. Conditions for child care and socialization have been created as priority areas of Education.

According to the 1991 report, there were 8743 kindergartens in the country. However, more than half of the kindergartens (4868) were privatized during the "privatization" period, most of them were empty and destroyed. In total, in 2000, the number of kindergartens in the Republic reached 1144 (1).

To date, the total number of preschool educational organizations in the country is 10,871. about 54.1% are state-owned and 45.9% are private preschool organizations.

The above figures explain the need to improve the quality of educational programs. Now let's analyze the programs of the last 10 years. During the adoption of the Balapan program for 2010-2020, such alternative programs as "Balbobek" and "first step", "Zerek Bala", "we are going to school", "Karlygash" worked in the process of education and education. And today we are working on a model training program.

In the years after independence, the only program that has implemented important obligations in the process of upbringing and education in preschool organizations is the Balbobek program. The educational program, taking into account national characteristics, passed an experimental platform and determined the first steps in raising children. The problem of treating

pupils as a person was considered as the main problem. It was one of the most pressing issues. The teachers of the preschool organization made it possible to perceive each child as a person, to form the necessary competencies and skills through various methods. The development of effective ways of forming a child's personality also belongs to the balbobek program was. The priority was given to social and emotional skills. Given that most of the personality development consists of the above skills, it indicates the content priority of the program.

In order to effectively organize children's time, the program identified several priority areas. The first is that the main activity is to be organized in a playful way. It is not difficult to understand the importance of the game in the life of my child if we take into account the opinion of V. V. Sukhomilinsky: "the game opens the door to life for the child and develops his creativity, without the game the formation of the mind is impossible." The game is the main phenomenon of human culture as a whole, its source. The game educates, socializes, develops, teaches the child. The child's motivation to play, communication, manifestations of behavior in preschool age will certainly be reflected even when the child grows up. At the same time, the program states that it is necessary to implement games, that is, actions through integration. Given that integration is the replenishment of the common understanding through information from different areas of knowledge, this is one of the priorities of the Balbobek program.

The structural and content value of the program was also unique. The continuity between the expected results, determined in accordance with the characteristics of each age, is one of the characteristic features of this program. The necessary competencies and obligations for individual teachers were also determined within the framework of the program.

The program "first step". A program for the upbringing and education of children aged 1-3 years. The main feature of the program, focused on five educational areas, is the orientation towards a specific age. The basics of content and structure are similar to the program "Balbobek". Priority is given to the game, the main tool in the upbringing of the child. At the same

time, the issue of labor training at an early age is considered.

The program "Zerek Bala". The program is designed for the education and training of children aged 3-5 years, guided by the principle of communication in the process of education and training, adaptation to project activities, cooperation with adults and peers. In the process of formation and development of the child's personality in five areas of education, the program was based on the principle of competence development. At the same time, the activities of children revealed the basics of management through the medium. The basic content of the program is focused on low-level competencies:

- health care;
- language and communication;
- cognitive;
- "what's wrong?";
- social.

Based on the individual characteristics of children, it is aimed at developing learning, guided by the principle of Group Communication. The main humanitarian goal is to work on the basis of the principle of multiculturalism.

Orientation "we go to school", a program aimed at the upbringing and education of children aged 5-6 years. It is aimed at ensuring the personal development and readiness of children for school. The main priority is the formation of a subject environment that works on the formation of competencies. He is guided by patriotism and cultural and historical traditions of our people in the development of cognitive, experienced, creative skills and other forms of activity. The organization of education and training of children is based on the following basic pedagogical principles;

- the position of cultural identity-the formation of multiculturalism, taking into account the culture of local, national and other nations;
- educational training-the formation in the child of the qualities of punctuality, discipline and responsibility, taking into account the mental and practical activities of the child.
- attitude to age and individual characteristics;
- consistency;
- understanding and activity;
- service communication;
- morality;
- visualization;

- creativity.

The structural-substantive content of the program is very similar to the above programs. The main goal is to integrate the work of education sectors, consisting of independent departments that are closely related to each other.

In 2016, a standard training program was approved. Since this year, work on alternative orientations has been discontinued. Preschool organizations worked only with one program. The program included separate sections by age (2). There was not much change in the expected results and competence indicators. The names of educational areas and partially educational services were combined. With the definition of the goals and objectives of the five educational areas, the individual obligations and expected results of each organized activity are determined.

In November 2022, the standard curriculum was re-published in updated content (3). If we analyze these programs, it is difficult to see very serious differences. The main reason this happens is that the creation structures are similar. The differences are only in partial terminology and expected results. The main reason for this is the similarity of the structure of the educational standard. At the same time, the program has a very low level of orientation work in the process of education and education. The main reason is the incorrect preparation of mandatory planning documents for the implementation of the program, and there are many conflicting points in the regulatory legal acts aimed at organizing educational and educational processes.

In conclusion, it is necessary to revise the existing normative legal acts. From the time of the examination, it is necessary to conduct a scientific and practical study. Due to the lack of continuity and consistency in the guidelines, we need to clarify the implementation tools. We think that the time has come to make a qualitative change in preschool education and education.

References:

1. Model for the development of pre-school education and training (March 15, 2021 No. 137);
2. Standard curriculum of preschool education and training (August 12, 2016 No. 449 of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan);
3. Standard curriculum of preschool education and training (October 14, 2022 KROAM No. 422).